

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

СУЧАСНИ ПРОБЛЕМИ ОСВІТИ

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CURRENT PROBLEMS OF EDUCATION

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Анотація

Питання освітніх проблем, як викликів сучасності ще не знайшли досить широкого висвітлення у вітчизняному філософському полі. Зазначається, що вони досить різноманітні, складні і відтворюють кризу освіти як глобальне явище. Освітні виклики свідчать, що освітні стратегії і практики не відповідають запитам інформаційного суспільства. Ця тенденція має місце і в українському суспільстві. Підкреслюється, що найбільш гострим викликом стає процес девальвації знань, їх імітація. Втрачається цінність знань як інтелектуального капіталу. Доводиться, що комерціалізація освіти призвела до появи в освітньому просторі такого явища як хабарництво, що невілює турботу людини про знання як турботу про себе, формує ринкову свідомість з позначкою «мінус». Технологізація освіти обумовила одержання знань за принципом «тут і зараз».

Abstract

The issues of educational problems as challenges of our time have not yet found wide enough coverage in the national philosophical field. It is noted that they are quite diverse, complex and reproduce the crisis of education as a global phenomenon. Educational challenges show that educational strategies and practices do not meet the needs of the information society. This trend also takes place in Ukrainian society. It is emphasized that the most acute challenge is the process of devaluation of knowledge, its imitation. The value of knowledge as intellectual capital is being lost. It is proved that the commercialization of education has led to the emergence of such a phenomenon as bribery in the educational space, which does not liberate a person's concern for knowledge as a concern for himself, forms a market consciousness with a "minus" mark. Technologization of education has led to the acquisition of knowledge on the principle of "here and now".

Keywords: human, education, challenges, information society, knowledge society, care for knowledge, education crisis.

Ключові слова: людина, освіта, виклики, інформаційне суспільство, суспільство знань, турбота про знання, криза освіти.

Modern society is represented quite diverse: information, technological, risk, network, knowledge, post-modern, each of which has the right to exist, because it emphasizes its polyvariance, because, according to S.V. Proleyev, modernity shows that there is no common world, that the end of tolerance has come [5, p.25-29]. In these conditions, education as a means of creation of man by man, a means of creation of his life and being undergoes significant changes. According to experts from different fields of education (philosophers, educators, psychologists, teachers, etc.), it needs trans-

formation. Today, as V. Shamrai notes, the question becomes relevant: does not the world appear before our eyes, in which education in its established original vocation simply will not have a place? [11, c.90].

The question is quite complicated, it arose in the situation of the crisis of education, a crisis that affected not only educational practices, theoretical and methodological technologies, educational institutions, training of pedagogical resources. Experts note that the crisis is felt in all major dimensions and components of educational activities. It has become global and has not bypassed our country. The current education system in

Ukraine requires reforms. This is recognized not only by experts in the field of education, but also by teachers, teachers, students and pupils. It is necessary to update the system of professional development of pedagogical staff of educational institutions of different levels. The adopted "Law on Higher Education" (2014) and "Law on Education" (2016) defined the main directions of education transformation. However, these efforts will not be effective if the subjects of education do not contribute to this, if self-realization, self-creation remain outside the motives and life principles of the individual. There is a paradox: the formation of the "knowledge society" and at the same time the crisis of education.

Researchers of the "knowledge society" point out that 1) it has a multiplicity and plurality of different forms and levels of knowledge; 2) it provides an opportunity for each person, regardless of the conditions of his/her existence, but in accordance with them, to adapt most effectively to modern reality; 3) the "knowledge society" is a society "compatible in the use of knowledge"; 4) it is a necessary opportunity for the survival of society and the preservation of humanity.

The "knowledge society" requires new theoretical and practical grounds of education, which are able to overcome the crisis educational situation, the challenges that have emerged in the educational reality and which relate to the dichotomy of tradition / innovation. Modern challenges to the existing model of education are aimed at developing and implementing such a model that would meet the requirements of time, the introduction of new paradigms. Today, despite the many useful developments, preference is given to the traditional paradigm of education based on the principles of scientism, monologism, authoritarianism, on the idea of a "one-dimensional" person - function. This paradigm has exhausted itself. As V.G. Tabachkovsky emphasized, the new paradigm should be based on the principle of assistance instead of normative and repressive. But this challenge as well as its implementation is very complex and controversial. Unfortunately, in today's education, pedagogical technologies are focused on the transfer of knowledge, not on the development of a creative person who must be responsible for his or her life and the lives of people both in the present and in the future.

In this plane, the principle of human care for education as care for oneself is actualized. That is why the use of reproductive or combined reproductive method cannot satisfy the subjects of educational activity. This method cannot serve the realization of caring for education as caring for oneself. Returning to the guideline "care for education as care for oneself" is a challenge of time. As long as a person does not try to fulfill the need for education, it cannot meet the basic needs of social development. It is no accident that experts in the philosophy of education emphasize an important theoretical and methodological innovation: "In the society of the XXI century, the way of relations and interactions becomes a network, which corresponds to the existence of a person in the form of a singularity" [11, p.92].

V. Shamrai, considering the "network-man" paradigm, notes that this is a new format of relations and it becomes a challenge for all institutions, certainly for education. Education, not only requires its transformation, but also calls into question its further existence in the established cultural sense. Therefore, education is not so much transformed, responding to the challenge of time, as reborn, acquiring completely different features. The direction and nature of these shifts are revealed on the basis of microsocial changes, marked by the concepts of networking, singularity and informationality.

Singularity, in contrast to the concepts of individuality and personality, according to the author, in the humanitarian and anthropological sense, is designed to capture such a state of human existence, when the activity and, in general, human life goes into the mode of entry-exit into various systems of contacts, which involves the de-substantiation of the person. This is a typical situation of existence in a network society, when the main social quality of a person is the use of the network, in the form of which social relations in general begin to exist [11, p.93].

You can object or agree with the author, but certainly this is the justification of a new educational paradigm, a new vision of the dichotomy tradition/innovation. With the position of V. Shamrai correlates the view on the need to change the model of education in the works of V.G. Andrushchenko, who points out that until society brings up a new generation of forward-looking people (in other words, creative people), we are doomed to "dig in the mud", "pour from empty to empty", to be in "constant transit of futility. The new philosophy of education ... is the philosophy of a person who exists in the realm of freedom" [1, p.11-13]. One of such models, according to researchers, is the model of an educated person. An educated person, firstly, is not so much a "knowing" person even with a formed worldview, but a person prepared for life, who is oriented in the complex problems of modernity, able to comprehend his place in the world.

Secondly, it is a person who knows, experiences, is spiritual and social. Thirdly, it is a person who is open to other cultural positions and values, a tolerant person. An educated person manifests himself as a creative competent person. A.A. Ivanchenko metaphorically compares this type of person with an "octopus" with a positivogenic "cancerous tumor" that spreads its beneficial "tentacles" or "metastases" to all vital areas of a person [4, p.65]. This trait is manifested in the ability of a person to make non-standard decisions in a situation of uncertainty and insufficient information, in the ability to respond to the challenges of modern human existence, which is characterized by plasticity, mobility, transience, constant changes. Today, as never before, questions arise that have concerned humanity since the beginning of antiquity. What is education? Are there "eternal" goals and standards of education? What is the meaning of education? How do classical and non-classical models of education coexist? What is the future of education? The understanding of the concept of "knowledge" is changing. In the research of scientists, "knowledge" is gaining a variety of meanings.

Its interpretation as a component of both human and social capital is becoming more and more common. Thus, the famous American philosopher and sociologist F. Fukuyama notes that abilities and knowledge are elements of human capital. Along with this statement, Fukuyama also believes that knowledge is the values of society and social groups, they are the matrix of intellectual work. He notes that knowledge is dominant in the development of the modern economy, social wealth and the human being [3, p.1-7]. Knowledge does not exist outside of man, outside of intellectual, mental work, it is the process and result of human activity. Innovative in the interpretation of the concept of "knowledge" is the point of view of the American researcher D. Teece, who along with the concept of "knowledge" offers the concept of "knowledge assets", which are transferred, "moved". It is always "sticky" because it sticks to people and organizations, it is flexible because it is constantly modified and regrouped [5, p.56]. According to the researcher - "knowledge society" requires such an understanding of "knowledge", because it is quite difficult in our time to talk about the sustainability of knowledge and its eternity.

Knowledge is "knowledge assets". And in this sense, they are a necessary component of the concept of a competent approach to learning. This position is proposed in the works of L. Edinson and M. Melowin, who emphasize that the totality of knowledge, practical skills, creativity constitute the essence of human capital [2, p.434].

The severity of the crisis is not due to its comprehensiveness, but to the fact that education increasingly does not meet its fundamental vocation. Its ability to ensure the self-reproduction of society and the continuity of cultural tradition is decreasing like a shagreen skin, evaporating literally before our eyes [11, p.90]. The present requires such guidance and practical actions, when knowledge becomes not just an addition to knowledge, but an attributive factor of human existence, for which knowledge is one of the necessary means of mastering the "art of life", the ability and willingness to live consciously and creatively, to live and be at the same time.

Education, as well as the definition of society in our time, is multivariate. It is a component of educational reality, a form of being of a person and society, human capital, a means of life, a means of human creation, etc. It is one of the socio-cultural universals, without which the existence of man and society is impossible. The content of education depends on the historical conditions of its existence. Therefore, it is no coincidence that the analysis of education in its various manifestations is becoming quite relevant. This is evidenced by the works of both foreign and domestic experts. In the philosophical field, the study of education began in antiquity: Plato and Aristotle founded educational institutions, models of education. This tradition exists to this day, enriching and developing. Thus, at the end of the XX - beginning of the XXI century, such a scientific field as "philosophy of education" appeared. In the philosophy of education, it is becoming increasingly important to analyze the crisis of education, its challenges, conflicts, contradictions, and to propose

models of education that correlate with the state of today's society. On these issues, the works of V.P. Andrushchenko, M. Beilin, A.I. Boyko, O. Gomilko, L. Denisco, M. Kul'taieva, M. Karpets, S. Klepko, V. Kremen, I. Proleyev, N. Radionova, I. Stepanenko, V. Shamrak, K. Yakovenko and others deserve attention.

The crisis of education is the presence of challenges both to the content of education and to the subjects of education, to the emergence of a technological person and the technologization of education, challenges associated with the "fourth stage" of the technological revolution and its consequence - the emergence of a "knowledge society". Education in the form that developed at the end of the twentieth century does not take into account the current global crisis of civilizational development, cannot resist it, let alone contribute to its overcoming. In this sense, it becomes one of the research tasks to clarify the educational challenges of our time. Modern education is expected to provide accessibility and convenience of consumption of "goods", which are specific knowledge and skills. Modern education is increasingly acquiring the quality of goods, appears in the context of market relations, as a component of the market of educational services. In the educational reality, such phenomena as "educational business", "education market", "educational services", "educational enterprises" have become a reality. They have a sense of existence, although they carry extremely negative consequences. Can society accept imitation of education as a feature of modern life, when there are more and more students who agree to pay money for each test or exam? Commercialization of education acquires a false feature - bribery. This is a significant challenge and threat to the further state of not only education, but also society.

The challenges concern both the subjects of education and the conditions of education. We cannot ignore the facts cited by the media that, for example, in Chirniivtsi region a significant number of teachers were unable to pass the EIT. This reality also takes place in other regions, because there can be no highly qualified teachers if they, especially in rural schools, teach language, computer science and mathematics. Teacher training institutes need to be reformed. Is such a form as in-service teacher training effective? In fact, neither work nor study. The challenge to both the form and content of training is, from our point of view, the results of external testing, which, unfortunately, are not very high quality. The trend of loss of intellectual potential and intellectual capital cannot be considered satisfactory.

A challenge to the modern educational system in Ukraine is the fact that more and more young people are trying to get knowledge abroad. Among those who have higher education - 80%, and among those who are looking for a job abroad, 88% want their children to study abroad. In 2021, 83 thousand of our young compatriots studied abroad. One of the reasons for this challenge is that, according to I. Verbytskyi, Executive Director of the SEDOS think tank, education abroad is often more affordable than in Ukraine if you are a capable person. Czech Republic and Germany offer free education for foreigners according to their constitution. In

France, the fee is symbolic (newspaper Express. Censor. Net). The motivation to study is lost. According to the State Service, one in four Ukrainians under the age of 24 did not have a job in 2021. The figure in 2021 reached 1.8 million people. There are 9 candidates for one vacancy. Academician of the NAS of Ukraine B. Hryniiov called the process of reducing the scientific potential of Ukraine a massive disaster, the consequences of which for society and the national economy have yet to be analyzed. Thus, in 2021, 25 thousand Ukrainians studied and worked in Germany, who receive guaranteed support from the state of this country. This picture shows the devaluation of knowledge, the lack of motivation to acquire knowledge, the understanding of knowledge as capital, without which neither social, nor professional, nor intellectual significance of a person is possible.

The educational challenge to the classical model in our time is media education - a component of media reality. According to P. Bourdieu, in modern society there is a mediatization of reality. This is an important conclusion in theoretical and practical terms. Based on this conclusion, V. Mansurova notes the following: "Media self-reflection and self-determination are becoming the ontology of the existence of modern society, and an individual who has received unauthorized access to communication has acquired the status of homo mediaties" [8, p.117]. It proves the ambivalence of the educational media challenge: self-expression for a media person is both a means of intellectual triumph and a manifestation of limited knowledge.

Trends in the development of media education that dominate in Ukrainian society affect its human security and at the same time show that traditional education is no longer able to meet the requirements for education. At the present stage, radical transformations in the information society are associated with the further development of media education, the Internet and the network. Media technologies are becoming decisive. Media education operates with such concepts as media educational space, media pedagogical technologies, media pedagogy, television education, video film, media images. Researchers are concerned about the fact that there is a narrowing of the range of interests of adolescents, the desire to create their own world, a departure from reality and one-on-one computer classes, which interferes with communication with peers, leads to social isolation and difficulties in interpersonal contacts [5, p.59].

There are new features of man: technological, electronic, integrated into the Internet, media-technological man, who clicks. Modern man in the information society uses in the process of life a variety of technologies, the latter lead to a change in education not only temporal but also spatial coordinates, allows us to see education as hypertrophied.

The Cartesian metaphor "man-machine" was replaced by the metaphor "man-program". As M. McLuhan noted in his works, the technological perspective and the associated metamorphosis of human being can

transform modern man into a new species that can be defined as Homo [9, p.79]. The point is that under the influence of various technologies the essence and existence of modern man acquires a different meaning. Technologies acquire a universal meaning, spreading to all situations where a person influences or tries to influence with their help all spheres of his life. Education does not stand outside this influence, because it exists in the realities of society as an ad hoc society of "reflective modernity". From now on, man needs to understand and define the limits of his being, to define a new question - the question of purposeful comprehensive development of himself as a human being in the process of communication with technology.

Thus, the modern educational reality manifested challenges that affect the process of education itself and the person in education, challenges that are aimed at overcoming the crisis in education. They are multivariate, as well as multivariate modern society and education. The challenges show that educational strategies in today's conditions do not meet the needs of the information society and the "knowledge society". There is a paradox, in Ukrainian society there is a tendency of devaluation of knowledge, imitation of education. The necessary value of knowledge as the status of the necessary human capital is lost. Thus, the development of modern education is a serious theoretical and practical problem of solving its challenges - the way to overcome the crisis in education.

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